

NSF Annual Report Summary

RCN: Advancing Research and Education Through a National Network of Campus Research Computing Infrastructures - The CaRC Consortium

Reporting Period: 01 Jul 2020 - 30 Jun 2021

Overview

CaRCC, the Campus Research Computing Consortium, is an organization of dedicated professionals developing, advocating for, and advancing campus **research computing and data**¹ and associated professions. Current focus areas include building community among research computing and data professionals, connecting the broader research computing and data ecosystem, professionalization and workforce development, and defining stakeholders and shared value propositions for the community at a time of accelerating change.

Vision: CaRCC advances the frontiers of research by improving the effectiveness of research computing and data (RCD) professionals, including their career development and visibility, and their ability to deliver services and resources for researchers. CaRCC connects RCD professionals and organizations around common objectives to increase knowledge sharing and enable continuous innovation in research computing and data capabilities.

Mission: CaRCC communities, working groups, and our collaborating partners, advance innovation and sustainability of RCD at academic, government, and non-profit institutions. CaRCC communities connect professionals across RCD roles and organizations, including those who design and operate systems, those who work with software and data, and those who engage directly with researchers. CaRCC working groups explore and develop effective strategies, leading practices, and products that empower researchers across campuses, and at regional, national, and international scales.

The figure below provides a high-level overview of the various streams of activity in CaRCC, which are described more fully below.

¹ “**Research computing and data**” involves people, scholarship, and resources supporting the needs of researchers and research leveraging compute, data, networking, and software, broadly defined, including the professionals who execute and support these efforts. Whereas entities supporting research computing and data historically emerged from operating and supporting high performance computing, the needs, capabilities and technologies have sufficiently broadened the scope of research information technology to include virtualization, support for the cloud, containers, middleware, workflows, data management, data movement, compliance and security, user training, support of instruction using advanced research computing and data, on-boarding into new technologies, and deep engagement (“facilitation”) to help guide researchers.

CaRCC Activities and Relative Timeline

NSF recently awarded funding for a pilot CoE to build upon the work of several CaRCC working groups and advance support for RCD Professionals. The new Research Computing and Data Resource and Career Center will create tools, practices, and professional development resources to support individuals and institutions. This **RCD CoE** will build upon a good deal of work that CaRCC has done to date, and in the sections below we describe where activities will transition to funding from this new grant.

People Network

As a community of research computing and data professionals, the “People Network” aims to foster, build and grow an inclusive forum for networking and sharing experiences (termed the “People Network”). Leveraging logistical support coordinated via CaRCC, this community executes synchronous and asynchronous opportunities to leverage collective and individual expertise, with focused discussion “tracks” reflective of professional activities (following the facings model described here: <https://carcc.org/rcd-professionalization/facings/>), akin to an ongoing virtual conference. Each track has its own email list, monthly community calls, and coordinators, whose role is to facilitate the ability of each track and the entire community to organize itself.

In the past year, the People Network saw continued growth in membership, based upon Google Groups/Slack channel membership:

<i>Track</i>	<i>Email 2021 members</i>	<i>Email 2020 members</i>	<i>Slack 2021 Members</i>
People Network	1065	750	266
Researcher-Facing	800	459	117
Systems-Facing	480	316	145
Data-Facing	566	390	68
Emerging-Centers	239	121	85

This growth was likely driven by the monthly calls for each Track, and by ongoing efforts to diversify topics and reach out to more RCD community organizations and professionals (see also the Engagement Operation Group). Monthly call announcement emails are sent not only to People Network list members, but to mailing lists of partner communities of RCD professionals. In this reporting period, these monthly announcements also began including regular community events hosted by these partners (e.g. US-RSE, EDUCASE RCD group, OU Virtual Residency). The Researcher-Facing Track is consistently reaching triple-digit call attendance, and Systems-Facing is also achieving these numbers for popular call topics. See Appendix A.1 for email mailing list graphs, and A.2 and A.3 for complete call attendance and tracking information.

With the addition of recording and distributing videos via YouTube in 2019, People Network calls are able to reach audiences beyond the real-time discussions in Zoom calls. The CaRCC YouTube channel currently has more than 150 regular subscribers, and a total of 1480 views this period (3384 overall). Almost all calls recorded during this period garnered double-digit view counts. See Appendix B.1 and B.2 for complete YouTube call video statistics. In light of the pandemic, and with the People Network already positioned as an "online" organization, the transition to all remote work, collaboration via electronics resources, etc. was effortless.

As call planning continues with track members driving the selection of call topics, the Coordinators have collaborated to identify opportunities for cross-track calls for topics of shared interest, including some all-track "plenaries" calls. For this reporting period, Network calls included 1 cross-track ("Service Models for Researcher-Purchased Computing and Data"), two plenary calls (PLENARY: Using Data to Benchmark your Research Computing and Data Program: The RCD Capabilities Model and Community Dataset, "CaRCC End-of-Year party"), and the "CaRCC Parade" in January 2021, for which the current leadership gave an overview and update of CaRCC activities and accomplishments to the attendees, similar to the "CaRCC Town Hall" presented at PEARC20.

For the next reporting period, several cross-track calls and plenaries, including ones initiated by members of the community, are currently planned. We will also continue to engage our communities via in-person and online venues, build stronger relationships with members of the Ecosystem, and more fully establish collaborative partnerships with CASC, EDUCAUSE, US-RSE, and other groups in the RCD space.

Professional development opportunities

Perhaps stating the obvious, the People Network Tracks, monthly calls, and ongoing ancillary efforts are resources for new and ongoing professional development for persons in the RCD space. As CaRCC continues to mature and other RCD organizations enter the space or mature, CaRCC will partner as appropriate for expanding People-Network opportunities. As a part of this reporting period's goals, two tracks have newly implemented a steering committee to assist with the efforts of the Track, provide a larger network of participants, expertise, and diversify the leadership. Thus, the Track Coordinator and Steering Committee roles also provide leadership development and succession planning for the Tracks and People Network.

Logistics Operational Group

The Logistics Group carries out ongoing activity that sets standards for and coordinates logistical aspects in support of CaRCC activities, including coordination of CaRCC-associated meetings and workshops, maintenance/improvements to common infrastructure (e.g. website and other outward communication mechanisms, internal documentation, logos, etc.), and liaising connections across various CaRCC activities and groups.

In the last year, work included the addition of a quarterly process by which the Leadership team (of group chairs and People Network coordinators) considers the activity and progress of various working groups, and makes decisions on the status of various groups, their representation in the Leadership team, and their representation on the CaRCC website, so that these do not fall out-of-date. Additionally, this review has helped some groups to make decisions and take sooner action on remaining work. Groups that were closed out included a Charter working group (after publishing a new Charter, see Products) and the Funding and Sponsorship group, both of which were temporarily suspended for planned revisit after initial progress, and the Ecosystem group (see below), which completed all planned work. The Logistics team will be responsible for future executing annual review of the Charter to determine if/when it needs further updates.

Looking into the next reporting period, the Logistics group led discussions around and implemented a no-cost-extension and budget reallocation to shift some planned workshops, and to extend and expand Engagement and communication work identified in the last year (see Engagement Operational Group).

Engagement Operational Group

The Engagement Operations Group, previously an Activity Group, is a team of individuals working to increase the visibility of and participation in CaRCC's community-driven activities, especially to organizations and individuals that are underrepresented. The group spent significant effort this reporting period into re-thinking how CaRCC presents itself to its community, to its partners and collaborators in the RCD ecosystems, to other non-engaged organizations, and to everyone else. The efforts have resulted in a number of additional activities that will benefit the organization in the long run.

The major group of activities has focused on CaRCC's messaging, predominantly through its website. The group has reviewed in detail the content presented by the different types of groups (People Network communities, Activity Groups, others) in order to more effortlessly present basic information, contact details, and showcase group products. Another example is re-envisioning the message for its current and future members on how to get involved with CaRCC ("How To Join") page, with explaining in more detail the various levels of participation one could engage at. In addition, the visualization of CaRCC's structure and its evolution deserved an update to better reflect how CaRCC has changed over time, including simplifying the presentation and giving a nod to ecosystem partners that are working on People Network activities that CaRCC has deferred (in the interest of collaborating instead of competing).

With the upcoming PEARC21 conference, Engagement is preparing and updating materials that can be used by CaRCC members and leaders when giving presentations and workshops, including slide and presentation templates, boilerplate text on "what is CaRCC" and CaRCC's mission, and logos & by-lines. These products are and will be made available beyond PEARC as standard 'marketing and communications' materials.

Additionally, ensuring that contributors and members feel valued and welcome, Engagement has organized participation rolls as a "Wall of Thanks", which can be used at conferences and workshops, and on CaRCC website itself. As CaRCC is a mostly volunteer organization, this acknowledgement will help build trust and confidence for the time well-spent on its activities.

For the next and final reporting period, Engagement will work toward providing useful templates and materials for its members and participants, make updates to the website to improve navigation and information dissemination, and continue its efforts to broaden CaRCC's reach and participation, including cultivating increased participation from within its ranks and by standardizing the way in which CaRCC and external groups engage and collaborate with one another.

RCD Capabilities Model Working Group

This model and an associated assessment tool allows institutions to assess their support for computationally- and data-intensive research via a series of questions across the various facings (i.e. researcher-facing, systems-facing, etc). This helps institutions identify gaps in their support and potential areas for improvement. It also can inform stakeholders (such as leadership or the libraries) about the broad needs and requirements of research computing and data in support of research and researchers. Each year, data will be aggregated across institutions, allowing us to gain insight into support levels across the community, and providing a baseline for institutions to benchmark against peers.

The RCD Capabilities Model completed the first annual Community Dataset, with 41 institutions contributing data. An analysis and report of the contributed data was published (zenodo.org/record/4344057), and has over 300 unique views (230 downloads) as of mid-June 2021. The figure below shows the distribution by facing (area of support) for the contributing institutions (the percentage values summarize the levels of support across a set of topics).

A set of EPSCoR-eligible institutions leveraged the model and their collective data to identify shared challenges, especially in comparison to institutions in non-EPSCoR states. They recently received funding for a workshop that will support more institutions using the capabilities model to assess their RCD support, analyze patterns across the EPSCoR community, and inform strategic planning (Building Research Cyberinfrastructure in EPSCoR Jurisdictions: Assessment, Planning and Partnerships, NSF-2033483, Gwen Jacobs, PI).

The 1.1 version of the Capabilities Model was released, which includes a series of updates and improvements in response to community feedback. Changes include a simpler access request

form, a simplified means of indicating relevance for selected topics, and a change in the weighting of factors to reflect community input.

A series of webinars, presentations, and office hours were provided by working group members to inform and support the community about the model, and how institutions are using it. Venues include PEARC, the Coalition for Networked Information (CNI) Fall 2020 meeting, and CaRCC and EDUCAUSE community meetings. The PEARC20 events included a workshop, a paper presentation (about the model), and a Birds of a Feather (BoF) session on preparing EPSCoR institutions to use the model. The model and/or the Community Dataset report will also be the topic of PEARC21 events including a workshop, a paper presentation, and a second EPSCoR-related BoF.

The PEARC workshops provide training and professional development opportunities, helping staff to learn effective tools for program assessment, for building strategic partnerships on their campus, and for developing strategic plans for RCD programs.

In the coming year, we will continue to support the 1.1 version of the model (including office hours, webinars, etc.), we will manage the 2021 Community Dataset activity, and will produce the 2021 Community Dataset report (which will integrate 2020 and 2021 data). This work is in parallel with work that will be conducted under the new RCD CoE to develop a new more robust implementation of the assessment tool as well as a dataset portal. The existing data from the 1.0 and 1.1 versions will be imported into the database supporting the new portal.

RCD Professionalization Working Group

This working group created an HR Job Family Matrix specifically for RCD Professionals that can be used by institutions to properly classify RCD Professional roles. The WG continues to disseminate and develop new frameworks and approaches to guide conversations between Human Resources leaders and Research Computing and Data leaders around attracting, retaining, diversifying, and developing research computing and data and cyberinfrastructure talent. In the figure below, we provide an overview of the progress to date.

RCD Professionalization Timeline

June 22, 2021

As facilitating research continues to increase and broaden, it is important now to understand comprehensively the state of RCD staffing across the country. Most institutions are isolated from one another with regards to sharing basic information on staffing roles, position types, and pay grades, which are important to HR and hiring managers. Many professional societies publish an annual salary survey (e.g., IEEE) as do some marketing firms (e.g., Dice), but none of these focus purely on academic institutions, and this makes it challenging for local HR to interpret and make use of them. Data from a census will provide a measure of equity across institutions and positions, which in turn can aid in effectively attracting, retaining, and diversifying RCD professionals. Current work includes an RCD Professionals Workforce Survey, and work to document Career Arcs into and among RCD professional roles. Both of these threads of activity began activity this year, and both will ramp up as part of the new RCD CoE.

The aim of the Workforce Survey is to provide the first large data set on the composition of the research computing and data (RCD) workforce in terms of demographics, job responsibilities, job types, compensation, and perceptions of the RCD field. The study is limited to the United States due to varying data privacy laws and research requirements internationally. The survey opened on June 1, 2021 and will run through September 2021 with the goal of 1000 respondents.

During the next year survey results will be widely shared with the community and provide data to:

- Describe the current research computing and data professionals workforce to provide a measure of equity across institutions and positions, which in turn can aid in effectively attracting, retaining, and diversifying RCD professionals

- Compare this workforce to related academic and technical workforces in terms of demographics and educational background
- Characterize the types of job positions present in the field and the work done by different job positions
- Generate data for use by individuals, hiring managers, and human resources professionals in the field on salary, job titles, job families, and job responsibilities

The sub-group focused on Career Arcs began meeting regularly in early 2021, and has begun gathering narratives of RCD professionals. Ongoing discussions and analysis are focused on key elements that influence career arcs, on the different patterns of how individuals move into and among RCD roles, and on effective means of presenting this as a useful resource (including both narratives and a visualization of some sort). This preliminary work will be picked up under the new RCD CoE and carried forward, and so the Career Arcs work under this current grant will soon cease.

Decadal Survey Interest Group

Formed in 2019 and reinvigorated in 2020, the Decadal survey interest group's efforts are largely concentrated on Objective 4, advancing RCD and strategic planning. Via the decadal survey process, output, and anticipated recommendations, we will demonstrate the importance and value of engaging and empowering RCD professionals as equal partners with agencies and researchers in determining CI/RCD strategies, defining and influencing technology pathways to advance scientific discovery, and executing to deliver solutions. On the one hand, many outside the CI/RCD community view non-tenure track RCD professionals as "support" staff at best. However, from the RCD community members' perspective, a view that is fully supported by our track record, is that RCD professionals have essential roles to play in defining and delivering the spectrum of technologies and capabilities required to propel research broadly and across disciplines. The work of the Decadal Survey will result in community consensus about priorities for investment in CI and will shape the field and RCD profession for years to come.

Over the last year, the Decadal Survey Interest Group added new participants for additional diversity and breadth; reviewed and discussed existing Decadal Surveys from various science domains; drafted a Charter; drafted a set of questions for an "informing the decadal survey" pre-survey; and identified stakeholders and potential advocates in professional organizations, science domains, and federal agencies. Importantly, we have also engaged the assistance of a professional evaluator, Dr. Lizanne DeStefano (with financial support contributed by NCSA), for assistance throughout the process of framing, administering, and interpreting the survey. The group is also preparing a timeline and associated deliverables for its work. Those will include a Decadal Survey Workshop and associated summary report.

The Interest Group plans to transition to a Working Group by the end of calendar year 2021.

Ecosystem Interest Group

The Ecosystem working group began in the fall of 2018 as the Ecosystem Workshop Planning working group. Following the productive April 2019 Ecosystem workshop and subsequent plenary panel at PEARC19, the working group expanded to include all interested workshop participants and others to develop plans for future work resulting in a paper presentation at PEARC20 and completing the objectives of the Ecosystem working group. During the fall of 2020, following the NSF funded workshop on the CI workforce (award #2036534, <https://www.rcac.purdue.edu/ciworkforce2020> and co-chaired by CaRCC co-PI Brunson) several participants formed a Community of Communities working group. This new working group is building from both the ecosystem working group efforts and the CI workforce workshop recommendations. Additionally, this work aligns with the newly-funded NSF CI CoE demo pilot “Advancing Research Computing and Data: Strategic Tools, Practices, and Professional Development” (award #2100003) which (among other things) will work together with other organizations that support RCD professionals to advance the goals developed by the ecosystem workshop, CI workforce workshop, and community of communities working group participants on the path towards a RCD Resource and Career Center.

Appendix

Section A.1, People Network and Track mailing list membership counts over time. This graph represents the current counts to date.

Section A.2, People Network Call Data Call (reverse chronological): Statistics recorded for each *-Facing Track call (via Zoom). As attendees were added to the email lists, the new users added are also tracked.

<i>Date</i>	<i>Track</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>Max Cnrxn Count</i>	<i>Sign-in Count</i>	<i>New Users to P-N list</i>	<i>New Users to Track list</i>	<i>Call doc link</i>
6/17/2021	Systems Facing	Two unique approaches to developing CUI Compliant Systems	54	46			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RYujFGjQmMHeel-Cekgf0v41aUMJJXwTC7TQCannPIXY/edit?usp=sharing
6/1/2021	Data Facing	OSF Integrations	40	35			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Q4MSz9LP0Y9hRtBfG1JV0WeHJFKOdZa3dQC1rGRajGw/edit#
5/20/2021	Systems Facing	Clusters in the Sky: How Canada is Building Beyond IaaS Cloud with Magic Castle	72	49			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1annsHPUiLje_znBgMUfQyIFvKyc5HmZn7LzBVu23pWc/edit?usp=sharing
5/19/2021	Emerging Centers	Directions for the Emerging Centers	27	23			
5/13/2021	Researcher Facing	Workflow Tools for Portable, Reproducible Data Analysis	121	91	14	12	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1EmHnPvWSsVUKHqzVNcf_BZyg8wFi6bXuUAqauoQKxgE/edit?usp=sharing
5/4/2021	Data Facing	Data Feminism	49	37			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1NeYIDJpo5ObdO9pD1ZrAu3GjYJHypM6D3BQRsH-sCSE/edit#
4/21/2021	Emerging Centers	New Resources Available to the National Research Community: Jetstream 2, Bridges 2, and Anvil	34	26			
4/15/2021	Systems Facing	Experiences and Advice for Large and Small Data Centers – Cooling	69	39			
4/8/2021	Researcher Facing	On Measuring the Impact of Training	122	100	21	21	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Yh2Ct80tMCN0QWHLQ52mtOzMOXzv1ozngBLQRQKWJuo/edit?usp=sharing
4/6/2021	Data Facing	Digital Scholarship Platforms and Workflows	41	35			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1gtPM9JeOP-N2xX8ozasRmTp8FojBFvYVwpvVQHPl1Fhro/edit#
3/18/2021	Systems	Enabling Science Collaborations with	76	54			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1JQ6unxa-INvgh-ITfSDRPki_P-fNAgeabCoA7sYm

	Facing	Secure and Flexible Service Deployment					el/edit?usp=sharing
3/17/2021	Emerging Centers	Experiences from institutions doing RCD	40	30			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ytyd5yJkaY_pHaXGvHWKIKE7uZzGEW2FQRzMnuuj6YQ/edit#
3/11/2021	Researcher Facing	All About Orienting Researchers to Research Computing and Data Resources	113	101	12	12	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Dq9O2QuOFRoSINIXwksYbqx4bjNOunKbNDcf5nZ0Sfk/edit
3/2/2021	Data Facing	PLENARY: Using Data to Benchmark your Research Computing and Data Program: The RCD Capabilities Model and Community Dataset	69	60			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1gc2b31RTIVAQfhccbe3tdXGXH_k1bOLT_tAQMUGlvGI/edit#
2/18/2021	Systems Facing	Geddes Composable Platform - Purdue's Kubernetes-based private cloud solution	84	63			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZG1HslfN2b72VaEppeKRStUEq5WEwinRfRviYa3kl4s/edit?usp=sharing
2/11/2021	Researcher Facing	Supporting Researchers with Containers	174	136	39	40	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IGzJlJq2RdrHle6mjmO6MKRsk6xJ0Wx_KKF67nMAOCsE/edit
2/2/2021	Data Facing	Casual Tuesday Community Roundtable	23	16			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1UNyZr58vD1ro1Sp8EZY08Sfy_-4eAqf5TnvpPgtafB0/edit#heading=h.8ihgwws8ogic
1/21/2021	Systems Facing	HPC Cluster Operating Systems Options	147	104			https://docs.google.com/document/d/115FdHlvr8eHkladejS1E_qpGiiHZXaoC7HsdqZKh7Ug/edit?usp=sharing
1/14/2021	Researcher Facing	All About CaRCC (..and Beyond the Researcher-Facing Track)	108	96	13	13	https://docs.google.com/document/d/12c1w3s-Q02Ucv0tO4UGtPyouPIUJ-C3KPFkPRZd_Epw/edit#heading=h.xrfr62de1vgq
1/5/2021	Data Facing	Python for Big Data	72	54			
12/16/2020	Emerging Centers	CC* Program overview	70	46			
12/01/2020	Data Facing	UMLS	32	25			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1XsikY6xy1zLBmxq5C-hBXCf-9CCU--Q66v1bgXgIVl4/edit#
11/12/2020	Researcher Facing	Profiling and Optimizing R Code In Your Workflows	96	85	24	25	https://docs.google.com/document/d/18uu_pwFLQaqwOgNP6mJw24f9Z5jU79zNvkuNQVXeaik/edit#heading=h.xrfr62de1vgq
11/3/2020	Data	Teaching Data Skills Remotely: Check-in	45	40			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1qXk

	Facing						WfmcilSMxJ-F0D-UAaYggaVZh4bSFVlnkKv w35F0/edit#
10/21/2020	Emerging Centers	CASC Organization and where it fits within the community	27	19			
10/15/2020	Systems Facking	Basic Cloud Bursting with Azure & VMWare	67	37			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1dabVKQoHehEpspxYEiXiuDHep9pQiOYBWAfJgpyBYPU/edit?usp=sharing
10/8/2020	Researcher Facing	Writing More Equitable Job Postings	81	74	17	17	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1L6LhTv-X3pCigOQxnnMS1bWtT0paIR0R9WrE7g3luRw/edit#heading=h.ow38i5w0kxuz
10/6/2020	Data Facing	The Power of Electronic Lab Notebooks	51	31			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1EuKbMu7Da-H3azbGng0ti9a2AQP3S01WOGTW4qmOwQ/edit?usp=sharing
9/17/2020	Systems Facing	Overview of HPC File Systems and One Site's Experience	115	57			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1212CVvxkJoUPyhdpYG12DXiUxgWUXliskYzEBCJmkc/edit?usp=sharing
9/11/2020	Data Facing	An Institution-wide Examination of Data Needs: NSF EPOC Deep Dive at the University of Cincinnati	47	29			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1iZZXxSWvjJmEXEwb-rhpAjAf_iw_7JnhWEI-JQf81GM/edit#
9/10/2020	Researcher Facing	Supporting Researchers in the Cloud: One University's Approach	98	80	20	22	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1DYpOAtX43YhJGe4HAHB357fZQnAUVVnjWefzFIdydfi/edit
8/20/2020	Multi Track	Service Models for Researcher-Purchased Computing and Data	136	91			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vGOdK6iElbnqs2QIUxZsdUgPcDCGa9io-l6gObWxels/edit?usp=sharing
7/16/2020	Systems Facking	OURRstore: Big Data on a Small Budget	53	35			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1GES1ph2z3llswx7miyYTyMxnbc16AO5Ky-dUsaqKvCY/edit?usp=sharing
7/15/2020	Emerging Centers	Drafting Policy	23	21			
7/9/2020	Researcher Facing	Big Data, Big Compute Solutions, A Community Discussion	96	84	9	12	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1yJTrudDs_fpQGSjjsVJPpfv1_izDIvmcrUWGSTTVOD8/edit
7/7/2020	Data Facing	What data to keep? -- Making decisions about confocal microscopy data	38	31			

Section A.3, People Network Call Data (by Track, reverse chronological)

Date	Track	Topic	Max Cnxn Count	Sign-in Count	New Users to P-N list	New Users to Track list	Call doc link
6/1/2021	Data Facing	OSF Integrations	40	35			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Q4MSz9LP0Y9hRtBfG1JV0WeHJFKOdZa3dQC1rGBRajGw/edit#
5/4/2021	Data Facing	Data Feminism	49	37			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1NeYlDjpo5ObrdO9nD1ZrAu3GjYlHvpM6D3BORsHsCSE/edit#
4/6/2021	Data Facing	Digital Scholarship Platforms and Workflows	41	35			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1gtPM9JeOP-N2xX8ozasRmTp8FoiBFvYWpxVQHP1Fhro/edit#
3/2/2021	Data Facing	PLENARY: Using Data to Benchmark your Research Computing and Data Program: The RCD Capabilities Model and Community Dataset	69	60			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1gc2b31RTIVAOfhcbe3tdXGXH_k1bOLT_tAQMogIvGI/edit#
2/2/2021	Data Facing	Casual Tuesday Community Roundtable	23	16			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1UNYzr58vD1ro1Sp8EZY08Sfy_-4eAqf5TnyvPgtEb0/edit#heading=h.8ihgwws8oojc
1/5/2021	Data Facing	Python for Big Data	72	54			
12/1/2020	Data Facing	UMLS	32	25			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1XsikY6xy1zIbmxg5C-hBXCf-9CCU--Q66v1bgXgIVl4/edit#
11/3/2020	Data Facing	Teaching Data Skills Remotely: Check-in	45	40			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1qXkWfmcilSMxJ-F0D-UAaYqgaVz4bSEVLNkkVw35F0/edit#
10/6/2020	Data Facing	The Power of Electronic Lab Notebooks	51	31			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1EuKbMu7Da-H3azbGng0ti9a2AQPS3SO1WOGTW4qmQwO/edit?usp=sharing
9/11/2020	Data Facing	An Institution-wide Examination of Data Needs: NSF EPOC Deep Dive at the University of Cincinnati	47	29			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1i7ZXxSWvjImEXEwb-rhpAjaF_jw_7JnhWEI-JQf81GM/edit#
7/7/2020	Data Facing	What data to keep? -- Making decisions about confocal microscopy data	38	31			
5/19/2021	Emerging Centers	Directions for the Emerging Centers	27	23			

4/21/2021	Emerging Centers	New Resources Available to the National Research Community: Jetstream 2, Bridges 2, and Anvil	34	26			
3/17/2021	Emerging Centers	Experiences from institutions doing RCD	40	30			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vtvd5yJkaY_pHaXGvHWKIKE7uzZGEW2FQRzMnuuj6YQ/edit#
12/16/2020	Emerging Centers	CC* Program overview	70	46			
10/21/2020	Emerging Centers	CASC Organization and where it fits within the community	27	19			
7/15/2020	Emerging Centers	Drafting Policy	23	21			
5/13/2021	Researcher Facing	Workflow Tools for Portable, Reproducible Data Analysis	121	91	14	12	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1EmHnPyW5sVUKHqzVNcf_BZyg8wFI6bXuUAqaauQKxgE/edit?usp=sharing
4/8/2021	Researcher Facing	On Measuring the Impact of Training	122	100	21	21	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Yh2Ct80tMCNQQWHLO52mtOzMOXzv1ozngBLOQKwWuo/edit?usp=sharing
3/11/2021	Researcher Facing	All About Orienting Researchers to Research Computing and Data Resources	113	101	12	12	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Dq9O2OuOFRoSINIXwksYhgx4bjNOunkbNdcf5nZ0Sfk/edit
2/11/2021	Researcher Facing	Supporting Researchers with Containers	174	136	39	40	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1GzJlq2RdrHle6mimO6MKRsk6xJ0Wx_KKF67nMA0CsE/edit
1/14/2021	Researcher Facing	All About CaRCC (.and Beyond the Researcher-Facing Track)	108	96	13	13	https://docs.google.com/document/d/12c1w3s-Q02Ucv0tO4UGtPyouPIUJ-C3kPEkPRZdEpw/edit#heading=h.xrfr62de1vgq
11/12/2020	Researcher Facing	Profiling and Optimizing R Code In Your Workflows	96	85	24	25	https://docs.google.com/document/d/18uupwFlQaqwOgNP6mJw24f9Z5jU79zNvkuNOVXeak/edit#heading=h.xrfr62de1vgq
10/8/2020	Researcher Facing	Writing More Equitable Job Postings	81	74	17	17	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1L6LhTv-X3pCigOOxnnMS1bWtT0paIR0R9WrF7g3IuRw/edit#heading=h.ow38i5w0kxuz
9/10/2020	Researcher Facing	Supporting Researchers in the Cloud: One University's Approach	98	80	20	22	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1DYqOAtx43YhJGe4HAHB357fZQnAUUVniWefzFldydfi/edit
7/9/2020	Researcher Facing	Big Data, Big Compute Solutions, A Community Discussion	96	84	9	12	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vJTrudDs_fpOGSjjsVlPpfv1_izDlvmcrUJWGSTTVQp8/edit
6/17/2021	Systems Facing	Two unique approaches to developing CUI Compliant Systems	54	46			https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RYuifFGjQmMHeel-Cekgf0v41aUMJXX

						wTC7TQCanPIXy/edit?usp=sharing
5/20/2021	Systems Facing	Clusters in the Sky: How Canada is Building Beyond IaaS Cloud with Magic Castle	72	49		https://docs.google.com/document/d/1annshPUiIje_znBgMUFOYlFvKyc5HmZn7LzBVu23pWc/edit?usp=sharing
4/15/2021	Systems Facing	Experiences and Advice for Large and Small Data Centers – Cooling				
3/18/2021	Systems Facing	Enabling Science Collaborations with Secure and Flexible Service Deployment	76	54		https://docs.google.com/document/d/1JQGunxa-INygh-ITfSDRPki_P-fNAgeabCoA7sYmel/edit?usp=sharing
2/18/2021	Systems Facing	Geddes Composable Platform - Purdue's Kubernetes-based private cloud solution	84	63		https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZG1Hs1fN2b72VaEpeKRStUEq5WEwlnRfRyiYa3kl4s/edit?usp=sharing
1/21/2021	Systems Facing	HPC Cluster Operating Systems Options	147	104		https://docs.google.com/document/d/115FdHlvr8eHkladejS1E_qpGiiHZXaoCZHsdqZKh7Ug/edit?usp=sharing
10/15/2020	Systems Facing	Basic Cloud Bursting with Azure & VMWare	67	37		https://docs.google.com/document/d/1dabVKQoHehEpspxYEiXiuDHep9pQiOYBWAFlqpyBYPU/edit?usp=sharing
9/17/2020	Systems Facing	Overview of HPC File Systems and One Site's Experience	115	57		https://docs.google.com/document/d/1212CVvxkJoUPyhdvpYG12DXiUxqWUXliskYzEBCJmkc/edit?usp=sharing
8/20/2020	Multi Track	Service Models for Researcher-Purchased Computing and Data	136	91		https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vGOdK6iElbnqs2QIUxzSdUgPcDCGa9jo-16gObWxels/edit?usp=sharing
7/16/2020	Systems Facing	OURLstore: Big Data on a Small Budget	53	35		https://docs.google.com/document/d/1GES1ph2z3llswx7mivYTyMxnbcl6AO5Ky-dUsaqKvCY/edit?usp=sharing

Section B.1, People-Network YouTube Track Call recording statistics, current reporting period.

<i>Video title</i>	<i>Video publish time</i>	<i>Views</i>	<i>Watch time (hrs)</i>	<i>Subscribers</i>	<i>Impressions</i>	<i>Impressions click-through rate (%)</i>
<i>Totals</i>		1480	174.2515	25	20012	1.66
2020-07-07 Data-facing Call: What Data To Keep?	7/13/20	77	6.3464	1	668	1.8
2020-07-09 Researcher-Facing Call: Big Data, Big Compute Solutions	7/13/20	31	1.1438	0	1386	0.79
2020-07-15 Emerging Centers Call - Policy	7/15/20	7	0.4673	1	525	0.76
2020-07-16 CaRCC Systems-Facing - OURRstore: Big Data on a Small Budget	7/17/20	79	8.6138	1	1094	1.19
2020-08-20 CaRCC Multi-Track: Service Models for Researcher-Purchased Computing and Data	8/20/20	80	12.3497	0	1458	1.58
2020-09-01 Data-facing Call: An Institution-wide Examination of Data Needs	9/11/20	29	2.7456	1	631	1.43
2020-09-17 Systems-Facing - Overview of HPC File Systems and One Site's Experience	9/17/20	79	13.8555	1	1286	2.41
2020-10-06 Data-facing Call: The Power of Electronic Lab Notebooks	10/13/20	43	3.705	0	1297	1.31
2020-10-08 Researcher-Facing Call: Writing More Equitable Job Postings	10/14/20	54	2.8128	1	399	3.01
2020-10-15 Systems-Facing: Basic Cloud Bursting with Azure & VMWare	10/15/20	71	9.0209	2	899	1.11
2020-10-21 Emerging Centers - Coalition for Academic and Scientific Computing	10/22/20	12	1.503	0	264	2.65
2020-11-01 Data-facing Call: Teaching Data Skills Remotely	11/4/20	31	1.2031	1	313	2.24
2020-11-12 Researcher-Facing Call: Profiling & Optimizing R Code in Your Workloads	11/19/20	59	7.404	2	556	2.16
2020-12-16 Emerging Centers Track Call: NSF CC* Program and EPOC	12/17/20	31	4.6205	0	589	1.87

2021-01-05 Data-Facing Track Call: Python for Big Data	1/12/21	33	0.7881	0	694	1.15
2021-01-14 Researcher-Facing Call: All About CaRCC	1/20/21	72	4.5724	2	385	2.86
2021-01-21 Systems-Facing: HPC Cluster Operating Systems Options	1/21/21	127	19.4508	4	942	1.7
2021-01-27 CaRCC Emerging Centers Track January 2021 Call	2/3/21	12	0.9478	0	370	1.08
2021-02-02 Plenary: The RCD Capabilities Model and Community Dataset	3/12/21	27	4.0812	1	504	0.6
2021-02-11 Researcher-Facing Call: Supporting Researchers with Containers	2/17/21	80	11.075	0	470	2.13
2021-02-18 Systems-Facing: Geddes Composable Platform - Purdue's Kubernetes-based private cloud	2/18/21	114	16.8546	3	619	2.91
2021-03-11 Researcher-Facing Track: Orientating Researchers to Research Computing + Data Resources	3/18/21	65	9.5932	1	487	2.26
2021-03-17 Emerging Centers Call: Research Computing and Data Center Experiences	3/18/21	11	2.1425	0	228	2.63
2021-03-18 Systems-Facing: Enabling Science Collaborations with Secure & Flexible Service Deployment	3/18/21	27	2.1909	0	549	1.28
2021-04-06 Data-facing Track Call: Digital Scholarship Platforms and Workflows	4/23/21	8	0.918	0	350	2
2021-04-08 Researcher Facing Call: On Measuring the Impact of Training	4/16/21	34	4.2957	0	629	0.79
2021-04-15 Systems-Facing: Experiences and advice for large and small data centers – cooling	4/15/21	35	4.3271	1	627	1.91
2021-04-21 Emerging Centers: New National Resources for Researchers-Anvil, Bridges-2 and Jetstream2	4/22/21	18	2.3189	0	240	2.5
2021-05-04 Data-facing Track Call: Data Feminism	5/5/21	57	5.1536	1	557	1.8
2021-05-13 Researcher-Facing Call: Workflow Tools for Portable, Reproducible Data Analysis	5/21/21	25	2.6589	1	308	1.62
2021-05-20 Clusters in the Sky: How Canada is Building Beyond IaaS Cloud with Magic Castle	5/20/21	38	4.4235	0	506	1.19
2021-06-01 Data-facing Call: Open Science Framework Integrations	6/15/21	3	0.0402	0	81	1.23
2021-06-17 Two unique approaches to developing CUI Compliant Systems	6/18/21	11	2.6278	0	101	7.92

Section B.2, People-Network YouTube Track Call recording statistics, all reporting periods.

<i>Video title</i>	<i>Video publish time</i>	<i>Views</i>	<i>Watch time (hrs)</i>	<i>Subscribers</i>	<i>Impressions</i>	<i>Impressions click-through rate (%)</i>
Totals		5604	554.8999	152	50739	3.97
2019-07-18 CaRCC Systems-Facing - Racktables for graphical HPC cluster management	7/19/2019	2239	161.34	4	10258	11.56
2019-10-17 CaRCC Systems-Facing - HTCondor's Philosophy of High-Throughput Computing	10/17/2019	286	36.5553	1	2624	4.95
2020-03-18 Emerging Centers Track Call: OpenOnDemand	3/18/2020	224	27.5401	1	1197	0.92
2019-03-21 CaRCC Systems-Facing - Ceph as a campus storage solution	4/16/2020	183	28.9446	2	1484	3.17
2021-01-21 Systems-Facing: HPC Cluster Operating Systems Options	1/21/2021	128	19.5158	5	949	1.69
2020-01-16 CaRCC Systems-Facing - HIPAA-aligned data and Public Cloud Platforms	1/16/2020	121	19.825	2	850	2.59
2021-02-18 Systems-Facing: Geddes Composable Platform - Purdue's Kubernetes-based private cloud	2/18/2021	114	16.8546	3	625	2.88
2019-05-16 Systems-Facing - Globus Installation and Configuration	5/16/2019	108	7.776	2	1827	2.08
2019-04-18 CaRCC Systems-Facing - CharlieCloud	4/18/2019	97	14.6441	3	953	3.36
2020-08-20 CaRCC Multi-Track: Service Models for Researcher-Purchased Computing and Data	8/20/2020	80	12.3497	0	1461	1.57
2021-02-11 Researcher-Facing Call: Supporting Researchers with Containers	2/17/2021	80	11.075	0	473	2.11
2020-09-17 Systems-Facing - Overview of HPC File Systems and One Site's Experience	9/17/2020	79	13.8555	1	1293	2.4

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2020-07-16 CaRCC Systems-Facing - OURRstore: Big Data on a Small Budget	7/17/2020	79	8.6138	1	1105	1.18
2020-07-07 Data-facing Call: What Data To Keep?	7/13/2020	78	6.3495	1	671	1.79
2020-04-16 CaRCC Systems-Facing - Direct to the chip warm water cooling HPC systems at OSC	4/16/2020	76	8.8746	1	1403	2.07
2021-01-14 Researcher-Facing Call: All About CaRCC	1/20/2021	73	4.573	2	386	3.11
2020-10-15 Systems-Facing: Basic Cloud Bursting with Azure & VMWare	10/15/2020	71	9.0209	2	901	1.11
2020-02-20 CaRCC Systems-Facing - UC San Diego Health's approach to meeting HIPAA compliance	2/20/2020	71	8.8972	0	1205	2.16
2021-03-11 Researcher-Facing Track: Orientating Researchers to Research Computing + Data Resources	3/18/2021	65	9.5932	1	487	2.26
2020-11-12 Researcher-Facing Call: Profiling & Optimizing R Code in Your Workloads	11/19/2020	59	7.404	2	559	2.15
2021-05-04 Data-facing Track Call: Data Feminism	5/5/2021	57	5.1536	1	565	1.77
2020-03-19 CaRCC Systems-Facing - Visualize And Analyze Your Network Activities Using OSU INAM	3/19/2020	56	2.2381	0	688	1.6
2020-10-08 Researcher-Facing Call: Writing More Equitable Job Postings	10/14/2020	54	2.8128	1	399	3.01
2019-11-14 Researcher-Facing Call: Open OnDemand User Experiences & Challenges	11/15/2019	50	5.28	0	513	1.95
2020-01-15 Emerging Centers Track Call: Gathering Researcher Use Cases	1/22/2020	50	1.9498	0	328	1.83
2019-06-20 CaRCC Systems-Facing - Open Discussion on supporting research computing on cloud	6/20/2019	46	3.9597	3	543	3.13
2019-12-05 CaRCC Systems-Facing - Developing an Interactive Tool for Exploring Data Storage Options	12/5/2019	45	4.6538	0	498	3.01
2019-12-12 Researcher-Facing Call: Researcher-Facing/CI-Engineer Metrics	12/12/2019	44	5.057	1	419	2.15

2020-10-6 Data-facing Call: The Power of Electronic Lab Notebooks	10/13/2020	43	3.705	0	1314	1.29
2020-02-13 Researcher-Facing Call: User support via Slack, open forums, Github repos & blogs	2/14/2020	43	6.2624	0	391	2.3
2020-05-14 Researcher-Facing Call: Working with Your Team Remotely	5/17/2020	43	3.5474	1	320	1.56
2019-10-10 Researcher-Facing Call: An Expansion of User Support Services at U Colorado Boulder	11/14/2019	43	3.4483	0	256	2.73
2019-09-19 CaRCC Systems-Facing - Providing a Unified Software Environment within ComputeCanada	9/19/2019	43	3.3491	0	664	1.66
2020-06-18 Systems-Facing - Intro to metrics collection w/ Prometheus and visualization w/ Grafana	6/18/2020	41	7.5233	1	905	1.66
2020-04-09 Researcher-Facing Call: Sharing Best Practices in Remote User Support & Training	4/14/2020	39	3.0799	0	277	0.36
2021-05-20 Clusters in the Sky: How Canada is Building Beyond IaaS Cloud with Magic Castle	5/20/2021	38	4.4235	0	513	1.17
2020-05-20 CaRCC Multi-Track: Student Workers	5/21/2020	35	2.8043	0	649	1.69
2021-04-15 Systems-Facing: Experiences and advice for large and small data centers – cooling	4/15/2021	35	4.3271	1	636	1.89
2019-08-15 CaRCC Systems-Facing - Storage and Data Management for a Mid-Scale Research Data Set	8/15/2019	35	4.018	0	686	1.31
2021-04-08 Researcher Facing Call: On Measuring the Impact of Training	4/16/2021	34	4.2957	0	632	0.79
2021-01-05 Data-Facing Track Call: Python for Big Data	1/12/2021	33	0.7881	0	696	1.15
2020-03-12 Researcher-Facing Call: User support via Ask.Cl and Locales	3/12/2020	32	3.5901	1	431	1.16
2020-12-16 Emerging Centers Track Call: NSF CC* Program and EPOC	12/17/2020	31	4.6205	0	594	1.85
2020-11-01 Data-facing Call: Teaching Data Skills Remotely	11/4/2020	31	1.2031	1	315	2.22
2020-07-09 Researcher-Facing Call: Big Data, Big Compute Solutions	7/13/2020	31	1.1438	0	1387	0.79

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2020-09-01 Data-facing Call: An Institution-wide Examination of Data Needs	9/11/2020	29	2.7456	1	634	1.42
2021-02-02 Plenary: The RCD Capabilities Model and Community Dataset	3/12/2021	28	4.0817	1	505	0.59
2021-05-13 Researcher-Facing Call: Workflow Tools for Portable, Reproducible Data Analysis	5/21/2021	28	3.4196	1	315	1.59
2021-03-18 Systems-Facing: Enabling Science Collaborations with Secure & Flexible Service Deployment	3/18/2021	27	2.1909	0	550	1.27
2020-01-09 Researcher-Facing Call: Handling Support Requests	1/13/2020	20	0.6123	0	358	1.68
2021-04-21 Emerging Centers: New National Resources for Researchers-Anvil, Bridges-2 and Jetstream2	4/22/2021	18	2.3189	0	240	2.5
2021-06-17 Two unique approaches to developing CUI Compliant Systems	6/18/2021	17	2.7609	0	135	7.41
2020-10-21 Emerging Centers Call - Coalition for Academic and Scientific Computing	10/22/2020	12	1.503	0	264	2.65
2021-01-27 CaRCC Emerging Centers Track January 2021 Call	2/3/2021	12	0.9478	0	375	1.07
2021-03-17 Emerging Centers Call: Research Computing and Data Center Experiences	3/18/2021	11	2.1425	0	233	2.58
2020-06-11 Researcher-Facing Call: How Are We Doing?	6/22/2020	10	0.0666	0	336	0.89
2020-02-19 Emerging Centers Track Call: Research Computing Strategic and Cyberinfrastructure Plans	2/19/2020	10	1.3461	1	266	0.75
2021-04-06 Data-facing Track Call: Digital Scholarship Platforms and Workflows	4/23/2021	8	0.918	0	356	1.97
2020-07-15 Emerging Centers Call - Policy	7/15/2020	7	0.4673	1	526	0.76
2020-04-15 Emerging Centers track call: COVID-19 developments	4/15/2020	5	0.0114	0	227	2.2
2021-06-01 Data-facing Call: Open Science Framework Integrations	6/15/2021	3	0.0402	0	89	1.12

